

Map of events in Przhevalsk uezd from July 4th to August 23rd in 1916

Kochkor valley
August 4th

Wagon train capture site

Bachino v.
(Balykchi)

Stolypino v.
(Kochkor)

Sary-Bulak post station

Naryn fort
(Naryn)

Koltzovka v.
(Bokonbaevo)

Barskoon v.

PRZHEVALSK
(KARAKOL)

Ivanitzkoe v.
(Tilekmat)

Mariinskoe v.
(Yrdyk)
Agricultural school

Teploklyuchenskoe v.

Sazanovskoe v.
(Ananyevo)

Ozerno-Folbaumskoe v. (Kuturgu)

Preobrazhenskoe v. (Tyup)

Karkyra valley
July 10th

Legend

- Events of August 7-11
- Events of August 12-14
- Events of August 15-23
- Black color – actions by Russian imperial forces
- White color – actions by rebels
- Uezd center
- Village of Russian settlers
- State border
- Uezd border
- Action of punitive squads
- Siege or battle
- Massacre or murder of Russians
- Massacre or murder of Kyrgyz
- Opium cultivation site
- Hotbed of rebellion
- Kurultai

* Dates according to pre-revolutionary calendar

